

EXAMINING THE DIGITAL LITERACY SKILLS OF LIBRARIANS USING TECHNOLOGY ACCEPTANCE MODEL (TAM)

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ABSTRACT

Digital literacy skills enable librarians to effectively use digital tools and technologies. This study examined the digital literacy skills of librarians in Pampanga and their relationship with the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), specifically Perceived Ease of Use (PEOU) and Perceived Usefulness (PU). Using a mixed-method approach, data were gathered through a validated survey and analyzed using descriptive, inferential, and correlational statistics. Results showed that librarians excel in navigating the internet, using mobile devices, and participating in online conferences but struggle with programming languages. A significant difference in digital literacy was found based on gender, age, and tenure as computer users. A strong, positive relationship was established between librarians' digital literacy and TAM dimensions, highlighting the importance of perceived usefulness and ease of use. The findings underscore the need for continuous capacity building in digital skills to enhance online library services in the new normal.

Keywords: *digital literacy, digital literacy skills, skills development, technology acceptance model (TAM)*

INTRODUCTION

Digital literacy skills make possible for librarians to use digital tools and technologies. According to Gie & Fenn (2019, citing Ukwoma, Iwundu & Iwundu, 2016) citing Digital literacy is defined by the British Educational Communications and Technology Agency (2010) as a combination of functional technology skills, critical thinking, collaborative skills, and social awareness.

Digital literacy refers to the ability to effectively use digital technology, communication tools, and networks to access, manage, integrate, evaluate, create, and communicate information ethically and legally. It involves navigating information in a nonlinear manner while integrating visual media to synthesize knowledge (Osterman, 2012). As an essential life skill in information societies, digital literacy encompasses the ability to understand and utilize information from diverse digital sources. Bawden (2008) describes it as the “ability to read, write and otherwise deal with information using the technologies and formats of the time.” Beyond technical proficiency, the essence of digital literacy lies in the capacity to comprehend and use information across multiple formats and sources, particularly when presented through digital platforms. Gilster (1997) emphasizes this perspective, defining digital literacy as “the ability to understand and use information in multiple formats from a wide range of sources when it is presented via computers.” This understanding of digital literacy is crucial in higher education, where students’ ability to navigate digital resources significantly impacts their learning experience (Nikolaos et al., 2019).

Digital literacy encompasses a range of cognitive and critical-thinking strategies that individuals use when engaging with digital information (Eshet, 2004; Osterman, 2012). Related terms often used interchangeably with digital literacy include *21st-century literacies*, *Internet literacies*, *multiliteracies*, *information literacy*, *information and communication technologies (ICT) literacies*, *computer literacy*, and *online reading comprehension (ORC)*. While each term has distinct definitions, they share common theoretical foundations under the broader concept of new literacies.

According to Ilomäki, Paavola and Lakkala (2016), the concepts digital competence and digital literacy have been used more frequently and are increasingly discussed, particularly in policy documents and policy-related discussions related to “*what kinds of skills and knowing people should have in a knowledge society, what to teach young people and how to do so*”.

The DigEuLit initiative produced the European Framework for Digital Literacy (EFDL), which was created to recognize the significance of digital literacy. It defines digital literacy as the awareness, attitude, and ability of individuals to appropriately use digital tools and facilities to identify, access, manage, integrate, evaluate, analyse, and synthesize digital resources, construct new knowledge, create media expressions, and communicate with others, in the context of specific life situations, to enable constructive social action; and to reflect upon this process (Martin, 2006).

The number of publications on digital literacy has increased almost exponentially over the last two decades. This abundance of scientific production is, of course, beneficial

because it increases knowledge on the subject, but it also poses a significant challenge for scholars: because of the proliferation of studies on the subject, it is extremely difficult to make sense of the field of research and fully understand its specificities and areas of interest. Scholars benefit from using digital and quantitative research methods to help them make sense of their field of study (Audrin & Audrin, 2022).

The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) is a theory of information systems that describes how users come to accept and use technology. According to Davis (1989), the success of a system can be determined by user acceptance of the system, which is measured by three factors: perceived usefulness (PU), perceived ease of use (PEOU), and attitudes towards usage (ATU) of the system (Davis, 1989). If a system is difficult to use, it is unlikely to be perceived as useful.

(Source: Davis, 1989, in Gie and Fenn, 2019, citing Chuttur, 2009)

In TAM, attitude towards usage is referred to as the evaluative effect of positive or negative feeling of individuals in performing a particular behavior (Gie & Fenn, 2019, citing Ajzen & Fishbein, 2000).

Research Questions

With the intention of developing a training program, the study seeks to evaluate the digital literacy abilities of Pampanga librarians. It specifically responds to the following queries:

- 1) What are the digital literacy skills possessed by librarians?
- 2) How do librarians acquire and improve their digital literacy skills?
- 3) What is the degree of proficiency of librarians in terms of the following?
 - a. Type of digital literacy skills
 - b. Type of digital searching tools used
 - c. Digital literacy levels

- 4) What is the degree of proficiency of librarians on the techniques used to acquire and improve digital literacy skills?
- 5) What is the difference in librarians' digital literacy in accordance with their demographic backgrounds (gender, age, district, home internet connection, and tenure of being computer user)?
- 6) What is the relationship between TAM's dimensions and digital literacy of the librarians?
- 7) What is the most dominant factor that influencing the digital literacy of librarians?

Null Hypotheses

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between perceived ease of use and digital literacy of librarians

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between perceived usefulness and digital literacy of librarians

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The study employed a quantitative-qualitative research design or mixed method, specifically exploratory research, and descriptive research for quantitative data. Exploratory research is conducted to investigate a problem that has not been clearly defined, has received insufficient attention, or is otherwise poorly understood. The primary goal of exploratory research, according to Stebbins (2019), is to generate inductively derived generalizations about the group, process, activity, or situation under study. The digital literacy skills of librarians will be identified in this study, as the techniques used to acquire and improve those skills. Meanwhile, descriptive research, according to Tang & Chaw (2016, citing Calderon, 2006), is the process of collecting, analysing, categorizing, and tabulating data about current conditions, practices, processes, trends, and cause-effect relationships, and then making adequate and accurate interpretations about such data with or without, or sometimes with minimal, statistical methods. The study made use descriptive research to describe the level of proficiency of librarians in terms of the types of digital literacy skills they have, the digital searching tools they use, their digital literacy levels, and the techniques they resort to in acquiring and improving their digital literacy skills.

Participants

Thirty-one librarians in Pampanga working in different types of libraries served as participants of the study. Figure 1 shows the demographic profile of the participants in terms of sex, age, district, home internet connection, and tenure of being a computer user.

Demographic Profile (N=31)	Variable	F	%
Sex	Male	18	58.06
	Female	13	41.94
Age	21-30 years old	2	6.45
	31-40 years old	8	25.81
	41-50 years old	13	41.93
	more than 50 years old	8	25.81
District	First	1	3.23
	Second	10	32.26
	Third	20	64.51
Home Internet Connection	Fiber	24	77.52
	Wireless	7	22.58
Tenure of being a computer user	6-10 years	8	25.81
	more than 10 years	23	74.19

Fig. 1. Demographic Profile of the Participants

Instrumentation

The primary data collection instrument was a survey questionnaire created by the researcher. There are three sections to the questionnaire. The participants' demographic information was gathered in Part I. Part II collected data on the participants' proficiency with digital literacy. Part III collected the methods used by the participants to develop and enhance their digital literacy abilities.

Validation of the Research Instrument. Two experts were requested to assess the applicability of the items under each section of the questionnaire as part of the face validation process, which was used to validate the questionnaire. The questionnaire was improved by considering the experts' comments and suggestions. Following the pilot testing, the Cronbach alpha was calculated to evaluate the questionnaire's internal consistency and reliability. As seen on Figure 2, the Cronbach alpha is 0.920 which is good.

	Mean	SD	Cronbach's a	Verbal Interpretation
Scale	3.41	0.325	0.920	Good

Fig. 2. Scale Reliability Test using JAMOVl

Data Collection

The data was collected using a Google form. After converting the validated research tool into an online form, the researcher shared the link to the online survey with the Pampanga librarians chatgroup as well as the individual Facebook accounts of the identified librarian participants.

Data Analysis

The data was presented, analysed, and translated using descriptive and correlational statistics, specifically frequency distribution, percentile, ranking, mean, standard deviation, analysis of variance (ANOVA), and Spearman's rank correlation coefficient. MAXQDA, a software for qualitative and mixed methods data analysis, was used to analyse the qualitative data.

MAXQDA. This software was used to describe librarians' digital literacy skills and the techniques they used to acquire and improve their digital library skills, as well as to answer research questions 1 and 2. Librarians' responses were categorized, and related codes were grouped and given a suitable theme.

Weighted mean. This was used to analyse and interpret librarians' level of proficiency in terms of the types of digital literacy skills, digital search tools used, and digital literacy levels, and to answer research question 3.

Analysis of Variance or ANOVA. ANOVA was used to determine whether there are significant differences in librarians' digital literacy skills based on their demographic backgrounds (gender, age, district, home internet connection, and tenure as a computer user) and to answer research question 4.

Standard Deviation. To determine the numbers' variance from the mean or average value and to respond to research question 3, the standard deviation was determined.

Spearman's Rank correlation coefficient. This was used to summarize the strength and direction (negative or positive) of a relationship between TAM's dimensions and the digital literacy of librarians as well as the most dominant factor influencing the digital literacy of librarians and to answer research questions 5 and 6.

Norms of Interpretation. To properly interpret the results of the computation the following norms for interpretation were utilized.

1. *The Likert Scale.* This was used to analyse librarians' options, which were described using a four-point scale value for assessing the types of digital literacy skills that librarians possess, the types of digital searching tools that librarians use, and the degree of proficiency of librarians' digital literacy levels.

Interpretation	Descriptive Rating	Range Interval
Very High	Highly Proficient	3.26 – 4.00
High	Proficient	2.51 – 3.25
Low	Unproficient	1.76 – 2.50
Very Low	Highly Unproficient	1.00 – 1.75

Types of Digital Searching Tools that Librarians Use

Interpretation	Descriptive Rating	Range Interval
Very High	Highly Proficient	3.26 – 4.00
High	Proficient	2.51 – 3.25
Low	Unproficient	1.76 – 2.50
Very Low	Highly Unproficient	1.00 – 1.75

Levels of Digital Literacy

Interpretation	Descriptive Rating	Range Interval
Very High	Highly Proficient	3.26 – 4.00
High	Proficient	2.51 – 3.25
Low	Unproficient	1.76 – 2.50
Very Low	Highly Unproficient	1.00 – 1.75

2. *Correlation Value Interpretation.* The correlation values in this study were interpreted following the table of correlation value interpretation developed by Bartlett, Kontrlik and Higgins (2001, citing Gie & Fenn, 2019) as shown below:

Correlation Value Interpretation

Correlation Value (r)	Descriptive Rating
± 0.70 – 0.99	Very Strong
± 0.50 – 0.69	Strong
± 0.30 – 0.49	Moderately Strong
± 0.10 – 0.29	Weak
± 0.01 – 0.09	Very Weak

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 3 presents the digital literacy skills possessed by librarians using code theory model through MAXQDA. Among the digital literacy skills identified by the librarians are creating and presenting content, learning collaboratively, search and validating information, and thinking critically and making sound judgment. The librarians' identified skills were added into the questionnaire.

Fig. 3. Digital Literacy Skills Possessed by Librarians

As to the techniques used by librarians in acquiring and improving their digital literacy skills. It was reported that librarians acquire and improve their skills through coaching and mentoring, continuing professional development, and skills assessment and development. These were also added into the questionnaire.

Fig. 4. Techniques in Acquiring/Improving Librarians' Digital Literacy Skills

Table 1 presents the degree of proficiency in terms of the digital literacy skills do librarians possess. Among these skills where librarians are highly proficient, using their mobile phones (mean = 3.74; SD = 0.421), navigating the Internet, and participating in an online conference (mean = 3.68; SD = 0.599) are in the top of the list. While it was reported that librarians are Unproficient when it comes to applying programming languages (mean = 2.13), they are nonetheless proficient on running multimedia applications (mean = 3.23; SD = 0.421), utilizing social networking apps (mean = 3.13; SD = 0.516), and using graphic design or editing software (mean = 3.06; SD = 0.771).

Table 1
Types of Digital Literacy Skills Do Librarians Possess

Digital Literacy Skills	Mean	SD	Interpretation
1. Applying programming languages	2.13	0.659	Unproficient
2. Creating and managing e-mail	3.55	0.497	Highly Proficient
3. Creating and presenting content	3.32	0.475	Highly Proficient
4. Learning collaboratively	3.42	0.620	Highly Proficient
5. Navigating the Internet	3.68	0.599	Highly Proficient
6. Participating in an online conference	3.68	0.599	Highly Proficient
7. Running multimedia applications	3.23	0.844	Proficient
8. Thinking critically and making sound judgment	3.61	0.615	Highly Proficient
9. Using graphic design or editing software	3.06	0.771	Proficient
10. Using mobile phones	3.74	0.421	Highly Proficient
11. Utilizing social networking apps	3.13	0.516	Proficient
12. Working with Software Productivity Tools	3.26	0.788	Highly Proficient

Table 2 shows the degree of proficiency of librarians on using different types of digital searching tools. Librarians are highly proficient in almost all digital searching tools particularly on websites (mean = 3.74; SD = 0.444), Web OPAC (mean = 3.55; SD = 0.55), and digital libraries (mean = 3.39; SD = 0.495) are on the top three in the list. This may be attributed to their exposure with these tools during the pandemic. Using subject gateways (in respected subject area) are the only digital search tool where it was reported that librarians are proficient (mean = 3.23; SD = 0.497).

Table 2
Types of Digital Searching Tools That Librarians Use

Digital Searching Tools	Mean	SD	Interpretation
1. Digital Libraries	3.39	0.495	Highly Proficient
2. Institutional Repositories	3.26	0.444	Highly Proficient
3. Online Bibliographic Databases	3.32	0.599	Highly Proficient
4. Open Access Sources/Open Educational Resources	3.32	0.540	Highly Proficient

5. Subject Gateways (in respected subject area)	3.23	0.497	Proficient
6. Web OPAC	3.55	0.505	Highly Proficient
7. Websites	3.74	0.444	Highly Proficient

Table 3 shows librarians' level of proficiency in various levels of digital literacy. Librarians excel at all levels of digital literacy, particularly the ability to find, use, and share information (with the computed mean scores of 3.71 and 3.65, respectively). Their proficiency in evaluating information and creating content using ICT and the Internet also received high marks.

Table 3
Librarians' Digital Literacy Levels

Digital Literacy Levels	Mean	SD	Interpretation
1. Ability to find information	3.71	0.461	Highly Proficient
2. Ability to use the information	3.71	0.461	Highly Proficient
3. Ability to share the information	3.65	0.486	Highly Proficient
4. Ability to evaluate the information	3.58	0.501	Highly Proficient
5. Ability to create content using ICT and the Internet	3.26	0.444	Highly Proficient

Table 4 presents the techniques do librarians resort to in acquiring and improving their digital literacy skills. Continuing professional development (mean = 3.48; SD = 0.508), skills assessment and development (mean = 3.39; SD = 0.495), and formal education and training (mean = 3.32; SD = 0.475) are top three in the list.

Table 4
Librarians' Techniques in Acquiring and Improving their Digital Literacy Skills

Digital Literacy Levels	Mean	SD	Interpretation
1. Coaching and Mentoring	3.29	0.528	Highly Proficient
2. Peer Training and Support	3.06	0.249	Proficient
3. Continuing Professional Development	3.48	0.508	Highly Proficient
4. Formal Education and Training	3.32	0.475	Highly Proficient
5. Skills Assessment and Development	3.39	0.495	Highly Proficient

A one-way ANOVA test was conducted to examine whether there is significant different in level of digital literacy among librarians from gender, age, district, home internet connection, and tenure of being a computer user. As show in Table 5, the p-values for gender, age, and tenure of being a computer user were 0.0031, 0.0117, and 0.0000, which were all less than 0.05, therefore, there was statistically significant difference in the level of digital literacy between librarians from gender, age, and tenure of being a computer user.

Table 5
Mean Scores and F-Values Difference in Level of Digital Literacy among Librarians with their Demographic Profile

Demographic Profile	Sources of Variation	Sum of Squares	d f	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Gender	Between Groups	1.3132	1	1.3132	10.36	0.00
	Within Groups	3.6752	2	0.1267	18	31
Age	Between Groups	1.3576	2	0.6788	5.234	0.01
	Within Groups	3.6308	2	0.1297	8	17
District	Between Groups	0	1	0	0.000	0.99
	Within Groups	4.9884	2	0.172	1	07
Home Internet Connection	Between Groups	0.0008	1	0	0.004	0.94
	Within Groups	4.9876	2	0.172	4	71
Tenure of Being a Computer User	Between Groups	3.0362	1	3.0362	45.10	0.00
	Within Groups	1.9522	2	0.0673	36	00

Hypothesis Testing

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between perceived ease of use and digital literacy of librarians

Based on the correlation analysis of Spearman Test presented in Table 6, a significant, positive, and strong relationship was found between perceived ease of use and digital literacy of librarians ($r = 0.510$, $p < 0.002$). The results revealed that any increase in perceived usefulness will increase the level of digital literacy of librarians as well. Hence, H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between perceived ease of use and digital literacy of librarians is rejected.

Table 6
Spearman Correlation between Perceived Usefulness and Digital Literacy of Librarians

Variable	Correlation Value (r)	Sig.	Interpretation
Perceived Useful	0.510	0.002	Strong

***Significant at $P < .01$ (two-tailed)*

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between perceived usefulness and digital literacy of librarians

Table 7 indicates that there is a significant, positive, and strong correlation between perceived ease of use and digital literacy of librarians ($r = 0.603$, $p < 0.001$). The positive significant relationship showed that a high perceived ease of use dimension can increase the level of librarians' digital literacy and vice versa. Therefore H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between perceived usefulness and digital literacy of librarians is rejected.

Table 7
Spearman Correlation between Perceived Ease of Use and Digital Literacy of Librarians

Variable	Correlation Value (r)	Sig.	Interpretation
Perceived Ease of Use (PEOU)	0.603	0.001	Strong

***Significant at $P < .01$ (two-tailed)*

Continuing Professional Development and Digital Literacy among Librarians

H₀₃: There is no significant relationship between continuing professional development and digital literacy of librarians

Table 8 shows a significant, positive, and strong relationship between librarians' ability to find information and their levels of digital literacy ($r = 0.818$, $p 0.001$). The positive significant relationship demonstrated that the presence of a continuing professional development mechanism increases librarians' digital literacy and vice versa. Therefore, H₀₃: There is no significant relationship between continuing professional development and digital literacy of librarians is rejected.

Table 8
Spearman Correlation between Perceived Ease of Use and Digital Literacy of Librarians

Variable	Correlation Value (r)	Sig.	Interpretation
Continuing Professional Development	0.619	0.001	Strong

***Significant at $P < .01$ (two-tailed)*

What is the most dominant factor that influencing the digital literacy of librarians?

Spearman Correlation Test was conducted on two dimensions (i.e., perceived ease of use and perceived usefulness) from Technology Acceptance Model and one independent variable (i.e., continuing professional development) with librarians' digital literacy. Based on the findings, it was found that continuing professional development showed a high correlation value of $r = 0.619$ compared to other variables. Meanwhile, perceived ease of use showed value of $r = 0.603$ and perceived usefulness showed value of $r = 0.510$. Meanwhile, perceived usefulness showed value of $r = 0.510$ and perceived ease of use showed value of $r = 0.603$. All three variables showed $R^2 = 0.120$, $R^2 = 0.280$, and $R^2 = 0.489$, respectively. This proved that perceived ease of use, perceived usefulness, and continuing professional development contributed 12.07%, 28.03%, and 48.90% variants change in librarians' digital literacy. Hence, the most dominant factor that influencing the digital literacy of librarians is continuing professional development.

Table 9
Spearman Correlation between Perceived Ease of Use and Digital Literacy of Librarians

Variable	Correlation Value (r)	Sig.
Perceived Ease of Use (PEOU)	0.603	0.001
Perceived Usefulness	0.510	0.002
Continuing Professional Development	0.619	0.001

***Significant at $P < .01$ (two-tailed)*

Conclusions

The goal of this study was to investigate librarians' digital literacy skills using the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM). Librarians have skills such as creating and presenting content, learning collaboratively, searching for, and validating information, and thinking critically and making sound judgment. It has been reported that librarians acquire and improve their digital literacy skills through coaching and mentoring, continuing professional development, and skills assessment and development.

Among these skills where librarians are highly proficient, using their mobile phones, navigating the Internet, and participating in an online conference, are in the top of the list. While it was reported that librarians are Unproficient when it comes to applying programming languages, they are nonetheless proficient on running multimedia applications, utilizing social networking apps, and using graphic design or editing software.

Librarians are highly proficient in almost all digital searching tools, particularly on websites, Web OPAC, and digital libraries, which are among the top three on the list. This could be due to their exposure to these tools during the pandemic.

Meanwhile, it has been reported that there is a statistically significant difference in the level of digital literacy among librarians based on gender, age, and tenure as a computer user.

The results of the study on the relationship between the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) and librarians' digital literacy revealed that there is a significant, positive, and strong relationship between librarians' digital literacy and perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use, which are two of the four main TAM dimensions. This means that any increase in perceived usefulness will also increase librarians' digital literacy. Furthermore, the positive significant relationship demonstrated that a high perceived ease of use dimension can increase the level of digital literacy in librarians and vice versa.

Interestingly, this study discovered that continuing professional development has a significant, positive, and strong relationship with librarians' digital literacy, which is also the most important factor influencing librarians' digital literacy.

Recommendations

The study's findings should assist library leaders and managers in any type of library in paying special attention to factors that have a significant, positive, and strong association in librarian acceptance to improve digital literacy. Librarians should be given enough opportunities to continuously acquire and improve their skills to improve library programs and services. The researcher suggested broadening the scope of study in terms of subjects and geographical area for future research. Another study could look into the other two TAM dimensions, Trust and Perceived Risks, in relation to digital literacy among librarians. Trust and Perceived Risks could be predicted as independent variables with some relationship to librarians' digital literacy.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The following items were considered in the conduct of the study: informed consent, privacy, and confidentiality. The researcher obtained the informed consent from all the study participants in compliance with the Data Privacy Act of 2012, emphasizing that their participation is voluntary and free of charge.

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